

Enhancing Credit Risk Assessment through Machine Learning: A Behavioral Scoring Approach

Omokhoba Blessing Yama¹, Chika Yinka-Banjo¹, Mary Akinyemi³

¹University of Lagos, University Road Lagos Mainland Akoka, Yaba, Lagos, Nigeria

²Third Austin Peay State University, 601, College Street, Clarksville, TN 37044

Abstract

The rapid advancements in artificial intelligence and machine learning have transformed decision-making landscapes in various industries, including finance. Effective credit risk management has become increasingly critical in the financial sector due to the rising prevalence of non-performing assets and fraud cases. This study is motivated by the challenges financial institutions face in predicting loan performance amid growing lending activities and the emergence of complex credit products.

This research integrates behavioral scoring insights into developing a machine learning model for credit risk management, thus providing deeper borrower profiling. A conceptual framework for credit risk assessment was established, involving data collection through focus group interviews and secondary sources. Behavioral data were analyzed to identify patterns, while financial data underwent preprocessing and feature engineering to ensure compatibility with machine learning algorithms.

Multiple machine learning models, including logistic regression, support vector machines, K-nearest neighbors, decision trees, extreme gradient boosting, light gradient boosting, and CatBoost, were trained and evaluated using accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score. The results demonstrated the effectiveness of ensemble methods, particularly CatBoost, which outperformed other models with an accuracy of 0.87, a precision of 0.88, a recall of 0.86, and an F1-score of 0.87. CatBoost's superior handling of categorical features and complex data interactions makes it a powerful tool for predicting loan defaults, offering financial institutions a more robust alternative for credit risk assessment.

Key Words: Behavioral scoring, Machine Learning, Credit Risk Assessment, CatBoost, Borrower profiling, Ensemble methods

1. Introduction

Artificial intelligence (AI), particularly machine learning (ML), has advanced rapidly in recent years, offering powerful tools for data analysis and predictive modeling (Rana, 2024) (Bharadiya, 2023). ML algorithms such as logistic regression, decision trees, random forests, support vector machines, and neural networks have transformed multiple industries by uncovering patterns in large datasets and enabling more accurate decision-making (Kurani et al., 2023).

A critical application of ML is credit risk management, which focuses on predicting the likelihood of borrower default (Parisi & Manaog, 2023) (Radojević et al., 2023). Effective credit risk management is essential for financial institutions, as credit losses directly affect profitability and long-term stability. However, traditional approaches, which often rely on historical data and basic statistical models, are increasingly inadequate in today's dynamic financial environment (Kumar et al., 2024).

The rapid growth of lending activities driven by automation, digital transactions, and the introduction of increasingly bespoke credit products has further increased the complexity of credit risk assessment. Financial institutions now face greater exposure to borrower default, and existing tools struggle to keep pace with these developments. There is therefore a pressing need for more robust, data-driven models that can evaluate and anticipate borrower behavior with greater accuracy.

This study seeks to address this gap by developing a machine learning model for credit risk management. Specifically, it aims to design a model that leverages behavioral scoring to improve the accuracy of credit risk assessment, while also investigating how behavioral data such as transaction patterns, spending habits, and overall financial behavior can provide deeper insights into borrower creditworthiness. By integrating diverse data sources and applying advanced ML techniques, the research intends to contribute to more reliable and proactive credit risk management strategies, thereby supporting the stability and sustainability of financial institutions.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Credit Risk

Credit risk refers to the potential loss faced by lenders when borrowers fail to meet repayment obligations (Khine, 2023). It remains a central concern in financial decision-making, with factors such as macroeconomic conditions, industry dynamics, and borrower-specific characteristics like income, credit history, and debt ratios shaping default likelihood (Almehdawe et al., 2021). To manage these risks, financial institutions employ credit scoring models and dedicate significant resources to predictive analytics (Ciampi et al., 2021). While application scoring assists in loan approvals, behavioral scoring supports portfolio monitoring and proactive measures against defaults (Wang et al., 2020). Effective credit risk management thus ensures both institutional profitability and borrower welfare (Farhan et al., 2020).

2.1.1 Credit Scoring

Credit scoring converts borrower attributes into numerical indicators to classify customers as low- or high-risk (Ampountolas et al., 2021) (Anderson, 2022). Traditionally, it is divided into application scoring, which evaluates new applicants using demographic and financial data, and behavioral scoring, which assesses existing customers using repayment histories (Bijak & Thomas, 2012) (Liu et al., 2022). By distinguishing between “good” and “bad” borrowers, credit scoring underpins informed lending decisions. However, reliance on conventional statistical methods limits adaptability to complex, evolving borrower behaviors (Wang et al., 2020).

2.1.2 Credit Risk Management in Nigeria

In Nigeria, credit risk management has been studied across multiple dimensions. Research has examined regulatory frameworks such as Basel II (Fadun, 2013), stress testing practices (Farayibi, 2016), and the effectiveness of risk management strategies in Deposit Money Banks (Akande & Alalade, 2019). Studies also highlight the moderating role of governance structures like risk management committees (Apochi & Baffa, 2022) and the relevance of sustainability codes in shaping financial practices (Weber, 2018). More recent work emphasizes the interplay between debt management and private sector sustainability in Nigeria’s economy (Shang et al., 2023). Collectively, these studies underscore the importance of strengthening risk management practices to ensure financial stability in the Nigerian context.

2.1.3 Machine Learning in Credit Risk Management

Recent advances in ML have expanded its applications in credit risk modeling, enabling financial institutions to analyze vast and complex datasets for default prediction (Boukerche & Wang, 2020) (Irfan et al., 2023). Van Liebergen (2017) highlighted use cases ranging from credit scoring and fraud detection to regulatory monitoring. However, while ML excels at predictive accuracy, its limited interpretability poses challenges for regulatory compliance and stakeholder trust. Studies demonstrate the value of ML algorithms in generating borrower risk scores (Wu & Pan, 2021) and tailoring lending conditions (Devan et al., 2023).

2.1.4 Other Related Work

Beyond conventional credit scoring, studies have explored hybrid ML models, ensemble techniques, and deep learning for credit risk prediction. These include fuzzy support vector machines (Wang et al., 2005), hybrid ensemble methods (Zhu et al., 2019), deep neural networks for transactional data (Babaev et al., 2019), and explainable AI approaches integrating monotonic constraints and SHAP explanations (Wang et al., 2020). Research has also incorporated alternative data sources such as call records and app-based marketplace data to enhance model performance (Oskarsdottir et al., 2020) (Roa et al., 2020). Collectively, these studies highlight the growing prominence of ML in financial risk management, though challenges remain around interpretability, regulatory alignment, and adaptation to local financial contexts.

3. Methodology

3.1 Conceptual Framework

The framework for this study is based on the need for proactive identification, assessment, and mitigation of lending risks to safeguard the stability of financial institutions. Machine learning models offer the ability to leverage borrower-level data both financial and behavioral to predict creditworthiness with improved accuracy. The conceptual framework in Figure 1 outlines the sequential stages involved in building, validating, and deploying the proposed model.

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework of the Credit Risk Management Model

3.2 Data Collection

Two types of data were utilized:

Primary data: Behavioral insights were gathered from 25 respondents using semi-structured focus group interviews, aimed at capturing borrower behavior patterns related to credit risk.

Secondary data: A historical dataset of 27,000 anonymized borrower records was obtained from a Microfinance Bank, with institutional approval and privacy safeguards.

3.2.1 Data Preprocessing

Collected datasets were cleaned and prepared for modeling. This included handling missing values, removing duplicates, detecting outliers, and formatting variables to ensure compatibility with the chosen machine learning algorithms. New features were derived from both financial and

behavioral attributes to enhance predictive power. These engineered variables provided more granular insights into borrower behavior and loan repayment likelihood.

3.2.2 Model Development

Machine learning algorithms were trained to identify relationships between input features and the target variable (loan default). The model was designed to capture both linear and non-linear interactions within the dataset. Model performance was assessed using standard classification metrics Accuracy, Precision, Recall, and F1-Score to evaluate predictive effectiveness and robustness in identifying potential defaulters.

4. Preliminary Tests and Results

4.1 Data Overview

The dataset combines primary behavioral insights from 25 borrowers and secondary data comprising 27,000 anonymized loan records from a Microfinance Bank.

4.1.1. Loan Characteristics and Borrower Profiles

Analysis of borrower details shows that loans were primarily issued for working capital in medium-scale enterprises. Borrowers were engaged across diverse sectors, with loan amounts ranging from ₦1,585.95 to over ₦10,000. Loan cycles varied significantly, from first-time borrowers to those with over 20 borrowing cycles.

4.1.2. Loan Status and Delinquency

Figure 2 illustrates the distribution of loan status, with non-delinquent loans forming the majority, though a significant proportion were delinquent. Delinquent loans showed overdue periods between 209 and 887 days, with penalties ranging up to ₦13,224.08. This highlights a persistent risk of repayment failure in certain borrower segments.

Figure 2: Distribution of loan status

4.1.3. Gender Patterns

As shown in Figure 3, female borrowers outnumber male borrowers, suggesting a higher engagement of women in SME financing. Importantly, Figure 4 indicates that female borrowers were less likely to be delinquent, supporting prior findings that women often display stronger repayment discipline (Hsu et al., 2021).

Figure 3: Graphical representation of the gender distribution

Figure 4: Bar graph showing delinquency by gender

4.2 Machine Learning Model Performance

Table 1 compares model performance across seven algorithms. Ensemble methods consistently outperformed traditional models. CatBoost achieved the highest overall performance (Accuracy = 0.87; Precision = 0.88; Recall = 0.86; F1 = 0.87), followed closely by LightGBM and XGBoost. Logistic Regression also performed well (Accuracy = 0.84), demonstrating that simpler linear models can remain effective. In contrast, KNN and Decision Trees underperformed, reflecting their limitations in handling high-dimensional and complex data.

Table 1: Model performance of different machine learning algorithms

Model	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1-Score	Nature of Model
Logistic Regression	0.84	0.85	0.83	0.84	Linear model
Support Vector Machines (SVM)	0.82	0.83	0.81	0.82	Non-linear model
K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN)	0.8	0.81	0.79	0.8	Instance-based learning
Decision Trees	0.78	0.79	0.77	0.78	Tree-based model

Extreme Gradient Boosting (XGBoost)	0.85	0.86	0.84	0.85	Ensemble model (Boosting)
Light Gradient Boosting Machine (LightGBM)	0.86	0.87	0.85	0.86	Ensemble model (Boosting)
CatBoost	0.87	0.88	0.86	0.87	Ensemble model (Boosting, specifically for categorical features)

4.3. Behavioral Insights from Focus Group Data

Behavioral survey data (n = 25) were analyzed to capture patterns in financial habits, borrowing practices, repayment challenges, and financial confidence.

4.3.1. Financial Habits

Respondents demonstrated proactive engagement with their finances (Figure 5). Most participants reported regularly checking account balances and making consistent contributions to savings, although 68% admitted to premature withdrawals (Figure 6). Savings motives were diverse, with emergency funds (60%), financial independence (48%), and education (40%) ranking highest (Figure 7). These patterns suggest that while savings culture is present, it remains vulnerable to liquidity shocks.

Figure 5: Bar chart showing the financial behavior of participants

Figure 6: Premature Withdrawal of Money from Accounts

Figure 7: Bar chart showing the primary reasons for saving money among the survey

Borrowing Practices

Borrowing behavior varied across the group. While nearly half of respondents (48%) reported borrowing funds to support business operations (Figure 8), an overwhelming majority (92.3%) maintained borrowing relationships with a single bank (Figure 9). This suggests institutional loyalty but also concentrated exposure to individual lenders.

Figure 8: Funds Borrowed for Business Operations

Figure 9: Pie chart illustrating the borrowing behavior of the survey respondents

Repayment Challenges

Delays in loan repayment were primarily linked to insufficient cash flow (48%), followed by administrative delays (32%) and banking-related issues (16%) (Figure 10). These findings indicate that repayment issues are often structural rather than attitudinal, underscoring the importance of incorporating liquidity and institutional efficiency indicators into predictive models.

Figure 10: Bar chart displaying the primary reasons for the delay in loan repayment

Financial Confidence

Most respondents expressed positive financial self-efficacy, with 80% reporting confidence or strong confidence in managing their finances (Figure 11). However, 20% indicated either neutrality or lack of confidence, suggesting variability in financial literacy and management capabilities.

Figure 11: Confidence in financial management

Income Levels

Monthly income distributions were concentrated in the ₦50,000–₦100,000 range (36%), with a smaller proportion earning ₦500,000 and above (12%) (Figure 12). This reflects a predominantly middle-income borrower profile, with implications for credit product design and repayment capacity.

Figure 12: Income distribution of respondents

5. Conclusion

This study evaluated the application of machine learning techniques for credit risk prediction in microfinance lending. Using financial and behavioral datasets, the results show that ensemble methods, particularly CatBoost, achieved the highest predictive performance (Accuracy = 0.87; F1 = 0.87). CatBoost’s ability to efficiently process categorical variables makes it especially suitable for borrower-level datasets where demographic and transactional features are critical. Logistic Regression also performed competitively, underscoring the continued relevance of interpretable models in credit risk contexts.

Behavioral insights from focus group data complemented the quantitative findings, revealing patterns of savings fragility, concentrated borrowing relationships, and repayment delays driven primarily by liquidity constraints. These findings emphasize the importance of integrating behavioral features alongside financial indicators to strengthen predictive accuracy and risk assessment.

The contribution of this study lies in demonstrating how machine learning, when enriched with borrower behavior, can enhance early detection of default risk in microfinance portfolios. For practitioners, the results highlight the potential of deploying CatBoost within loan approval processes to improve portfolio stability while extending financial inclusion.

References

Akande, F.I. and Alalade, Y.S.A., 2019. Effectiveness of Risk Management Strategies Among Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria. *Journal of Finance and Accounting*, 7(4), p.122.

Almehdawe, E., Khan, S., Lamsal, M. and Poirier, A., 2021. Factors affecting Canadian credit unions' financial performance. *Agricultural Finance Review*, 81(1), pp.51-75.

Ampountolas, A., Nyarko Nde, T., Date, P. and Constantinescu, C., 2021. *A machine learning approach for micro-credit scoring*. *Risks*, 9(3), p.50.

- Anderson, R.A., 2022. Credit intelligence and modelling: Many paths through the forest of credit rating and scoring. Oxford University Press.
- Apochi, J.G. and Baffa, A.U.M., 2022. Credit risk and financial performance of deposit money banks in Nigeria: moderating role of risk management committee. *European Journal of Accounting, Auditing and Finance Research*, 10(10), pp.98-115.
- Babaev, D., Savchenko, M., Tuzhilin, A. and Umerenkov, D., 2019, July. Et-rnn: Applying deep learning to credit loan applications. In Proceedings of the 25th ACM SIGKDD international conference on knowledge discovery & data mining (pp. 2183-2190).
- Bharadiya, J.P., 2023. The role of machine learning in transforming business intelligence. *International Journal of Computing and Artificial Intelligence*, 4(1), pp.16-24.
- Bijak, K. and Thomas, L.C., 2012. Does segmentation always improve model performance in credit scoring?. *Expert Systems with Applications*, 39(3), pp.2433-2442.
- Boukerche, A. & Wang, J., 2020. Machine learning-based traffic prediction models for intelligent transportation systems. *Computer Networks, Issue 181*, p. 107530.
- Ciampi, F., Giannozzi, A., Marzi, G. and Altman, E.I., 2021. Rethinking SME default prediction: a systematic literature review and future perspectives. *Scientometrics*, 126, pp.2141-2188.
- Devan, M., Prakash, S. and Jangoan, S., 2023. Predictive maintenance in banking: Leveraging AI for real-time data analytics. *Journal of Knowledge Learning and Science Technology* ISSN: 2959-6386 (online), 2(2), pp.483-490.
- Fadun, O.S., 2013. Implications and challenges of Basel II implementation in the Nigerian banking system. *Journal of Business and Management*, 7(4), pp.53-61.
- Farayibi, Adesoji 2016, Stress Testing in the Nigerian Banking Sector. Available online at: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=2836967> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.2836967>
- Farhan, M., Alam, H.M., Sattar, A. and Khan, S., 2020. Credit risk management in Islamic banking: A system thinking approach. *International Transaction Journal of Engineering, Management, & Applied Sciences & Technologies*, 11(16), pp.11A16J-1.
- Irfan, M., Elhoseny, M., Kassim, S. and Metawa, N. eds., 2023. Advanced Machine Learning Algorithms for Complex Financial Applications. IGI Global.
- Khine, M.M., 2023. Effect of Credit Risk Management Practices on Loan Performance Of UAB Bank (Doctoral dissertation, MERAL Portal).
- Kumar, N., Agarwal, P., Gupta, G., Tiwari, S. and Tripathi, P., 2024. AI-Driven Financial Forecasting: The Power of Soft Computing. *In Intelligent Optimization Techniques for Business Analytics* (pp. 146-170). IGI Global.
- Kurani, A., Doshi, P., Vakharia, A. and Shah, M., 2023. A comprehensive comparative study of artificial neural network (ANN) and support vector machines (SVM) on stock forecasting. *Annals of Data Science*, 10(1), pp.183-208.
- Liu, Y., Yang, M., Wang, Y., Li, Y., Xiong, T. and Li, A., 2022. Applying machine learning algorithms to predict default probability in the online credit market: Evidence from China. *International Review of Financial Analysis*, 79, p.101971.
- Óskarsdóttir, M., Bravo, C., Sarraute, C., Baesens, B. and Vanthienen, J., 2020. Credit scoring for good: Enhancing financial inclusion with smartphone-based microlending. arXiv preprint arXiv:2001.10994.

- Parisi, L. and Manaog, M.L., 2023. Optimal Machine Learning-and Deep Learning-driven algorithms for predicting the future value of investments: A systematic review and meta-analysis.
- Radojević, T., Kesić, M., Rajin, D. and Buténas, R., 2023. Presentation of disclosures related to credit risk of a certain bank. *The European Journal of Applied Economics*, 20(1), pp.66-92.
- Rana, S., 2024. Exploring the Advancements and Ramifications of Artificial Intelligence. *Journal of Artificial Intelligence General science (JAIGS) ISSN*, pp.3006-4023.
- Roa, L., Correa-Bahnsen, A., Suarez, G., Cortés-Tejada, F., Luque, M.A. and Bravo, C., 2021. Super-app behavioral patterns in credit risk models: Financial, statistical and regulatory implications. *Expert Systems with Applications*, 169, p.114486.
- Shang, M., Okorie, U.E., Hang, Y., Jin, X. and Ufua, D.E., 2023. National debt management and business sustainability in Africa's largest economy: A focus on the private sector. *Plos one*, 18(10), p.e0293582.
- Wang, Y., Wang, S. & Lai, K., 2005. A new fuzzy support vector machine to evaluate credit risk. *IEEE Transactions on Fuzzy Systems*, 13(6), pp. 820-831.
- Wang, Y., Zhang, Y., Lu, Y., and Yu, X., 2020. A Comparative Assessment of Credit Risk Model Based on Machine Learning: A case study of bank loan data. *Procedia Computer Science*, 174, 141-149.
- Weber, O., 2018. Financial sector sustainability regulations and voluntary codes of conduct: do they help to create a more sustainable financial system? Designing a sustainable financial system: Development goals and socio-ecological responsibility, pp.383-404.
- Wu, Y. and Pan, Y., 2021. Application analysis of credit scoring of financial institutions based on machine learning model. *Complexity*, 2021(1), p.9222617.
- Van Liebergen, B., 2017. Machine learning: a revolution in risk management and compliance?. *Journal of Financial Transformation*, Volume 45, pp. 60-67.
- Zhu, Y. et al., 2019. Forecasting SMEs' credit risk in supply chain finance with an enhanced hybrid ensemble machine learning approach. *International Journal of Production Economics*, Volume 211, pp. 22-33.